

HIGH HEAT RESISTANT EPOXY-BASED COMPOSITES

Swezin Than Tun^{1*} and Jonathan Hughes¹

¹ Composite Materials Research Laboratory, Toray Composite Materials America, Tacoma, WA, USA
* Corresponding author (Swezin.Tun@TorayCMA.com)

Keywords: Composite, Heat resistant, Micro-crack, Thermal oxidation, Tg

ABSTRACT

In recent years there has been increased interest in cost-savings and performance-enhancement for composite materials particularly in the field of high service temperature applications in extreme environments. It is known that epoxy-based composite materials have been limited to service temperatures of below 140°C, forcing the use of high temperature materials like bismaleimide (BMI) or super engineering plastics such as PEEK or polyimide composites. Toray research group has recently developed an epoxy-based resin system which has a glass transition temperature (Tg) of 235°C and a wet Tg of 210°C. This new resin system will serve to widen the use of epoxy to a higher temperature range. Preliminary testing shows very little oxidation and weight loss when exposed to 200°C for 1000hr. Moreover, this new resin system shows resistance to micro-cracking when cycled between hot and cold. Having similar processing conditions, good handlebility, and excellent mechanical performance as many conventional epoxy-based composite materials, this new resin system is suitable for most applications where a higher temperature material is needed.

1 INTRODUCTION

In recent years, fiber-reinforced composite materials using reinforcing fibers such as carbon fibers and glass fibers have been used as structural materials in aircraft, motor vehicles, sports applications such as tennis rackets, golf shafts, fishing rods, and general industrial applications; and the like owing to the high specific strength and specific elastic modulus thereof. Methods for producing fiber-reinforced composite materials include a method of using a prepreg as an intermediate sheet-like material involving impregnating reinforcing fibers with an uncured resin to form a prepreg, laminating multiple plies of the prepreg and subsequently heating to cure the resin, and a resin transfer moulding method of pouring a liquid resin into reinforcing fibers enclosed in a mould and subsequently heating the moulded resin for curing. Among these production methods, the method of using a prepreg has an advantage in that a fiber-reinforced composite material with high performance can be easily obtained because the orientation of reinforcing fibers can be strictly controlled and there is a high degree of freedom in designing a laminate configuration. Thermosetting resins are mainly used as the matrix resins in prepregs in view of availability and productivity; among the thermosetting resins, epoxy resins are suitably used in view of the adhesion between the resin and the reinforcing fibers, dimensional stability, and providing high mechanical properties such as strength and stiffness of the composite material obtained [1].

Currently there is a need to develop epoxy resin systems suitable for use in prepregs that are capable of higher service temperatures than the commercially available 180°C cure systems while also exhibiting excellent open hole compressive strength (OHC), as this property is often the limiting design criteria for structures [2-3]. There is also a need for epoxy resin systems offering processing flexibility; for example, epoxy resin systems that can be cured in both an autoclave or with OOA techniques. It is also desirable that the epoxy resin system maintains the processing and handling characteristics of a traditional epoxy/aromatic amine thermosets. These include tack, out life, and minimal volatility, all of which give epoxy resin systems an advantage over higher temperature thermosets such as benzoxazines and bismaleimides. This paper evaluates the resin and composite performance of a new 180°C cure epoxy resin system that can be cured in an autoclave. In addition to matching the mechanical performance of a commercially available 180°C cure system this new resin provides excellent hot/wet properties when tested at 180°C.

2 EXPERIMENTATION

2.1 Materials

The epoxy resin and curatives were supplied by various chemical companies. The aerospace grade resin samples (#3900 and new resin) were formulated in an in-house laboratory facility. Carbon fiber T800S-24K-10E unidirectional tape was supplied by Toray Composite Materials America Inc.

2.2 Methods

2.2.1 Resin Plate Molding

The formulated resin was preheated at 65 °C, degassed in a planetary mixer (FlackTek DAC-600.2 VAC-P) rotating at 2000 rpm for 3 min under vacuum to eliminate air bubbles, and poured into a metal mold with a 2 mm thick Teflon insert. The resin was heated to 177°C with a ramp rate of 1.7°C/min, allowed to dwell for 2 hours to complete the cure, and finally cooled down to room temperature. For a newly developed high heat-resistant resin, additional post cure of 210°C for 2 hours with a ramp rate at 1.7°C/min was performed.

2.2.2 Resin Properties

The complex viscosity, η^* , of the epoxy resin is measured by a Rheometer (ARES, manufactured by TA Instruments) using 40mm diameter parallel plates while increasing the temperature from 40°C to 170°C at a rate of 2°C/min with a strain of 10%, frequency of 0.5 Hz, and plate gap of 0.6 mm.

The prepreg tack and out life is relatively determined from a glass transition temperature (T_g) of an uncured resin. The T_g of the uncured resin is measured by a differential scanning calorimeter (DSC Q200, manufactured by TA Instruments) using the temperature from -50°C to 330°C at a rate of 10°C/min. The T_g of the uncured resin is determined by finding the slope transition using the half width calculation from the TA universal analysis software.

The resin flexural properties are determined from the 3-point bend test on the Instron mechanical testing machine. The cured resin plates were cut into 10 mm x 50 mm samples to prepare for the flexural testing. The samples were tested per ASTM D7264. For hot/wet (H/W) property, the samples were immersed in boiling water for 24 hours and then tested. All specimens were given a time of 3 minutes hold to reach the specific test temperature before testing.

The glass transition temperature of a cured resin is measured from a dynamic mechanical analyzer (ARES, manufactured by TA Instruments) using a torsion mode. The machine is set at 1.0 Hz heating from 50°C to 350°C at a rate of 5°C/min in accordance with SACMA SRM 18R-94. The cured resin plates were cut into 12.5 mm x 50 mm samples and tested accordingly. The T_g was determined from the storage modulus (G') curve and finding the intersection between the tangent line of the glassy region and the tangent line of the transition region between the glassy region and the rubbery region on the temperature-storage modulus curve. The temperature at that intersection was considered to be the glass transition temperature (T_g) commonly referred to as G' onset T_g . For hot/wet (H/W) property, the samples were immersed in boiling water for 24 hours and then tested T_g via the same method.

2.2.3 Composite Laminates Fabrication

Unidirectional prepreg used has FAW (Fiber Aerial Weight) of 192 g/m², resin content of 35.5 wt% giving the fiber volume of 55%. Fiber volume and resin content can be measured per ASTM D3529.

Prepregs using the resin system were made by hot-melt fabrication process from a 12" wide pilot machine. The layup and cure of the composite laminates were done per recommended cure cycles unless otherwise specified. The prepregs were cut and hand-laid up for autoclave cure. Table 1 summarizes the mechanical evaluation of interest. Both composite laminate using different resin systems were cured at 180°C for 2 hours with, a ramp rate of about 1.7°C/min under an autoclave pressure of 586 kPa. The high temperature epoxy system panels were given an additional free-standing

post cure in a conventional oven at 210°C for 2 hours. All specimens not otherwise specified were tested at room temperature dry condition (RTD) and specimens to be tested at an elevated temperature wet (ETW) were conditioned in deionized water at 71°C for two weeks. Specimens were given a time of 3 minutes hold to reach the specific test temperature before testing.

All the mechanical test coupons were cut per ASTM except for the interlaminar shear strength (ILSS) coupons which were cut per EN2563. For micro-crack test coupons, samples were cut into 75 mm x 50 mm specimens and exposed in an environmental chamber to the thermal cycle shown in Figure 1 below.

Figure 1: Cure Profile for Micro-crack Cycles

The thermal oxidative stability of the cured panels were determined from a mass loss between the initial weight and weight at several time intervals. The composite samples were exposed to an oxygen atmosphere for 1000 hours at 200°C and weight loss was measured at 168 hour intervals. The mass loss percentage was calculated from the following equation (1):

$$mass\ loss\ \% = \frac{w_f - w_i}{w_i} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

where: w_i = initial weight of sample before exposed to elevated temperature
 w_f = weight of sample at specific time after exposed to elevated temperature

2.2.4 Composite Laminates Mechanical Properties

The prepreg was cut and laid-up per Table 1 for the mechanical properties.

Test Panel	Test Condition	Ply Lay-up Configuration	Test Method
Tg (DMA)	Dry, Wet	[0°] ₁₂	SACMA SRM 18R-94
TS	RTD	[0°] ₆	ASTM D3039
OHT	RTD	[+45/0°/-45/90°] _s	ASTM D5766
OHC	RTD, ETW	[+45/0°/-45/90°] _{2s}	ASTM D6484
CAI	RTD	[+45/0°/-45/90°] _{3s}	ASTM D7137
ILSS	RTD	[0°] ₁₂	EN 2563
G _I C	RTD	[0°] ₂₀	ASTM D5528
Micro-crack	-	[90° ₂ , 0° ₄ , 90° ₂]	Optical Microscope

Table 1: Test methods and panel configurations

2.2.5. Failure Mode Observation

A Nikon OPTIPHOT-100 optical microscope was used to observe micro-cracking. The cross section sample of the cured composite was polished using a Struers automatic polishing machine with Struers polishing media to a 1 micron finish. Pictures were taken using an Olympus UC50 digital camera.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

2.3 Resin Properties

In theory, the glass transition temperature of a polymer is established from the free volume. The free volume is the space in a solid or liquid sample that is not occupied by molecules, that is the “empty space” between molecules. As an amorphous polymer is made up of both occupied volume and free volume, both will change as temperature is changed. Thus, glass transition temperature is the movement of chain segments in the polymer networks. Any structure or external condition will influence the chain mobility which then affects the value of glass transition temperature. Some of the factors that influence T_g are chain flexibility and rigidity, steric effects, intermolecular forces, copolymerization, cross linking and crystallinity, and plasticizer [4-5].

It is well known that increasing the crosslink density of the epoxy/amine network can increase the glass transition temperature, but the resin modulus of the cured network is impaired [6-8]. While maximizing both properties is often desired, having too high of a crosslink density can lead to an overly brittle network with poor elongation. Adding a thermoplastic resin to the thermosetting system can help mitigate this effect, however this often results in slightly decreasing the T_g .

To solve the aforementioned problem, many different epoxies with large backbone structures and high epoxy functionalities were investigated. Those epoxies increased the glass transition temperature by restricting the chain mobility, but they also provided high crosslink density creating brittle systems. A typical example of a brittle epoxy-based resin system with high T_g is shown in Figure 2. The polymer crosslink density can be calculated from the shear storage modulus of the G' curve [9]. The high crosslink density means high interfacial fraction and failures in craze formation as seen in a thermoplastic. In a thermoset system, the brittle failure mode can be expected if the crosslink density is high. Thus, a high performance epoxy resin was used in a new resin system (hereto after called PHT-334) to increase the glass transition temperature without increasing the crosslink density. As shown in Figure 2, PHT-334, containing the high performance epoxy, has a T_g of 235°C which is higher than 204°C of the standard #3900 epoxy. As the T_g of the new resin system is above 230°C, it can be anticipated that the laminate can withstand a higher service temperature of up to 180°C, as opposed to the conventional epoxy resin system. In addition, the new resin system has a low crosslink density as opposed to the typical brittle systems of high temperature epoxy resins.

Figure 2: Resin Tg Tested by Torsional DMA

The new resin system (PHT-334) containing the high performance epoxy has other benefits. As shown in Figure 3, the new resin system (PHT-334) has relatively the same resin flexural modulus as the standard #3900 epoxy when tested at room temperature. However, under hot/wet condition test, the retention of the modulus of the new resin (PHT-334) is relatively higher than #3900. The significant retention is seen at 121°C-H/W resin modulus (72% retention of PHT-334 vs. 66% retention of

#3900). It can be anticipated that a unique formation of crosslink structure helps reduced the free volume spaces in the network. The improved H/W resin flexural modulus is suspected to help with H/W compression strength of the laminate.

Figure 3: Resin Flexural Modulus Tested at Different Temperature

It is common for high performance thermosetting materials to have poor tack at room temperature due to their tendency to crystallize. In addition, some thermosets can react at room temperature giving poor out life and making the prepreg difficult to handle [5]. To solve the tack problem, low viscosity epoxy was incorporated in the new epoxy resin system (PHT-334) to reduce the viscosity at room temperature. To measure the out-life of the resin system, the Tg of the uncured resin was measured at 5 day intervals using DSC. As shown in Figure 4 both the PHT-334 system and the #3900 system demonstrated a similar slope of increased Tg over time. Thus the PHT-334 material has good tack and long out-life like #3900, that are needed for the manufacturing of large aerospace and rocket structures.

Figure 4: Resin Out-life at 23°C, 50RH%

2.4 Composite Laminates Properties

Unidirectional prepreg was made using T800S-24K carbon fiber and the performance of PHT-334 was compared to #3900 CFRP via testing per section 2.2.3 shown in Table 2. Tension and compression values are normalized to the CPT of 0.191 mm. The new resin system (PHT-334) has a superior T_g in both dry and wet conditions when compared to #3900, as expected due to the design of the resin chemistry. Due to its high T_g and the resin chemistry of the new resin system, the room temperature properties of the laminate tensile strength, interlaminar shear strength, and compression after impact are lessened compared to the standard #3900. However the open hole tension of PHT-334 is 22% higher than #3900.

The open hole compression strength of PHT-334 is the same as #3900 at room temperature test which can be expected that the resin flexural modulus is similar. However, under 121°C elevated temperature wet condition testing, the open hole compression strength of PHT-334 is 10% higher than #3900. In addition, under 180°C elevated temperature wet condition testing, the open hole compression strength of PHT-334 is over 50% higher than #3900. This compression strength is aligned with the resin flexural modulus data. PHT-334 also offers a 17% increase in interlaminar shear strength when tested at 200°C by having higher retention rate of shear strength at elevated temperatures. Overall, the CFRP mechanical properties of PHT-334 are suitable for service temperatures higher than 140°C. The toughening mechanism can be improved by incorporating some additives in the PHT-334 just like #3900 uses. Further investigation is needed for a toughened epoxy with high temperature capability.

Properties	Test Condition	Unit	#3900	PHT-334
Laminate T_g	Dry	°C	198	244
	Wet*	°C	166	204
TS	RTD (23°C)	MPa	2965	2690
OHT	RTD (23°C)	MPa	503	613
OHC	RTD (23°C)	MPa	296	298
	ETW** (121°C)	MPa	197	216
	ETW** (180°C)	MPa	107	174
CAI	RTD (23°C)	MPa	276	129
ILSS	RTD (23°C)	MPa	95.3	91.4
	ETD (200°C)	MPa	35.4	41.5
$G_I C$	RTD (23°C)	J/m ²	487	644

Table 2: CFRP Mechanical Properties (wet*:24h boil water soak, ETW**:71°C x 2weeks)

Thermal oxidative stability (TOS) is critical for determining the suitable service temperature for composites used in aerospace structures and their long term stability at those temperatures. This helps design engineers know how long a part can last at a particular temperature and still maintain its structural integrity. Traditionally epoxies have been regarded as inferior to other thermosets, such as bismaleimides, when considering TOS [11-12]. As seen in Figure 5. the new epoxy resin system (PHT-334) has mass loss less than 1.0 wt% where the standard #3900 has mass loss of 1.5 wt% from their original weight after exposed to 200°C for 1000 hours in a conventional air-circulated temperature control oven. This long term thermal oxidative stability will assist in safety design factors.

Figure 5: Composite Mass Loss After 1000hr at 200°C (Oven Baked)

2.5 Micro-cracking Observation

Micro-crack formation occurs when the material is exposed to rapid hot and cold cycling similar to what an airplane would experience during landing and takeoff. It is known that micro-cracks are formed in fiber reinforced plastic materials due to the difference in the coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) between the fibers and the resin [10]. The difference in CTE of polymers can be determined from the interfacial fraction between the polymers. As previously stated, the materials having low crosslink density have low interfacial fraction and display ductility [9]. Likewise, the new resin system displays ductility over a wider range of temperatures which can be resistant to interfacial fracture. In other words, it can resist the formation of micro-cracks.

An inch wide sample was cut from the thermally cycled panel and polished to examine a micro-crack at different magnifications under the microscope. Typically micro-cracks are formed through the ply, perpendicular to the fiber direction. It was predicted that the new resin system PHT-334 should have good micro-crack capability due to this theory. Figure 6. shows the representative cross sections of PHT-334 laminates that were exposed to the micro-crack cycle per Figure 1. The cross section shows no sign of micro-cracks perpendicular to the fiber direction or any cracks forming at the fiber resin interface.

Figure 6: Cross Section of PHT-334 CFRP Micro-crack Sample

2.6 Conclusions

PHT-334 shows similar properties to that of the current #3900 aerospace material at temperatures up to 121°C, such as mechanical performance and out time. However, above 121°C, in addition to having improved TOS stability, PHT shows superior properties to current 180°C cure epoxy systems. The PHT-334 resin system does not need the long processing times and complex bagging architecture needed for most BMI systems. Its ability to gel at lower temperatures enables the resin to be curable inside and outside the autoclave. This system, using the latest in high performance epoxy technology, has good capability in the range where traditional epoxy chemistries fail and BMI is not yet needed. This can reduce the cost of structures that are currently using materials that are rated to much higher use temperatures only because there is no alternative.

REFERENCES

- [1] C.A.May "Epoxy Resins: Chemistry and Technology". 2nd Edition, CRC Press, 1987.
- [2] R.F. Landel and L.E. Nielsen "Mechanical Properties of Polymers and Composites". 2nd Edition, CRC Press, 1993.
- [3] A.T. Nettles "Hot/wet Open Hole Compression Strength of Carbon/epoxy Laminates for Launch Vehicle Applications". National Aeronautics and Space Administration, 2009.
- [4] T.R. Crompton "Practical Polymer Analysis". Volume II, Springer Science & Business Media, 2012.
- [5] P.C. Hiemenz and T.P. Lodge "Polymer Chemistry". 2nd Edition, CRC press, 2007.
- [6] U.W. Gedde "Polymer Physics". 1st edition, Springer Science & Business Media, 2013.
- [7] F.W. Billmeyer "Textbook of Polymer Science". 3rd Edition, Wiley India Pvt. Limited, 2007.
- [8] V.R. Gowariker, N.V.Viswanathan, and J. Sreedhar "Polymer Science". 1st Edition, New Age International (P) Limited, 2005.
- [9] P.G. Whitten and H.R. Brown "Polymer Entanglement Density and its Influence on Interfacial Friction". Physical Review E, vol. 76, no. 2, pp 026101-1 - 026101-8, 2007.
- [10] T. Shimokawa, H. Katoh, Y. Hamaguchi, S. Sanbongi, H. Mizuno, H. Nakamura, R. Asagumo, H. Tamura "Effect of Thermal Cycling on Microcracking and Strength Degradation of High-Temperature Polymer Composite Materials for Use in Next-Generation SST Structures". Journal of Composite Materials, vol. 36, no. 7, pp 885-895 (2002).
- [11] J.D. Nam and J.C. Seferis "Anisotropic thermal-oxidative stability of carbon fiber reinforced polymeric composites". SAMPE, Anaheim, quarterly, 24, pp 10-18, 1992.
- [12] B. Mailhot, S. Morlat-Thérias, M. Ouahioune, and J.L. Gardette "Study of the Degradation of an Epoxy/Amine Resin, 1: Photo- and Thermo-Chemical Mechanisms". Macromolecular Chemistry and Physics, vol. 206, no. 5, pp 575-584, 2005.